

REINFORCED POLYMER CONCRETE PROPERTIES AND STRUCTURAL APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Polymer concrete is a composite material consisting of a synthetic thermosetting resin as binder and mineral aggregate. Polymer concrete shows a relatively low tensile strength compared with its compressive strength. Tensile reinforcement with steel or fibre reinforced plastic rebars may be required for structural applications. The polymer concrete dealt with in this paper was composed of an orthophthalic polyester resin with shrinkage reducing additives and dried crushed quartz sand with grain size up to 5 mm.

The materials properties of the polyester concrete obtained at 23, 40 and 60 °C are given in the following table.

Table: Materials properties of polyester concrete

Temperature [°C]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Flexural strength [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]
23	128	25.1	14.1
40	120	24.4	--
60	118	19.3	12.7

Polymers and therefore also polymer concretes are viscoelastic materials whose long-term deformation depends on stress and temperature. Creep tests in bending were performed over 1000 hours with a stress equal to 50 % of the corresponding short-term strength. The creep deformation was extrapolated to 25 years by applying the relation $\epsilon = \epsilon_0 + m \cdot t^n$ derived by Findley 1958. The influence of warming on the long-term deformation was much greater than on the short-term strength with the creep deflection at 60 °C being about 4 times the deflection at 23 °C.

Structural elements (beams and slabs) reinforced with GFRP (glass-fibre reinforced plastic) bars or steel rebars in the tension zone and steel rebars in the compression zone were tested in bending. The GFRP rebars had a tensile strength just above 1000 MPa. The steel had a yield strength of about 550 MPa. The modulus of elasticity of the GFRP was 45000 MPa and essentially smaller than that of the steel with 200000 MPa.

The beams were so designed that the maximum tensile force the reinforcement was able to carry was the same for the GFRP (at tensile strength) and for the steel (at yielding). The amount of steel per volume was about 1.8 times that of the GFRP bars. Up to the cracking load, which was higher for the beams with steel reinforcement, the deflection was independent on the kind of reinforcement. Afterwards, the deflection of the GFRP reinforced beams became about 4 times the deflection of the beams with steel rebars. The deflection corresponds to the relation of the modulus of elasticity of both materials.

For polyester concrete slabs, which are used in level crossings, the tension reinforcement of steel rebars was replaced by GFRP bars by an amount of 1.4 times the volume of the steel. The behaviour under bending load was similar to the beams. The deflection of the slabs with GFRP tension reinforcement was about twice the deflection of the slabs with steel reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: Polymer concrete, temperature, reinforcement, glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP), structural elements

INTRODUCTION

Polymer concretes are well established materials and generally applied when special requirements, which cannot be met by cement concrete, have to be fulfilled. Binders for polymer concrete are synthetic thermosetting resins such as unsaturated polyester, vinylesters, epoxies or acrylates. These resins are generally modified and may contain additives, e.g. for shrinkage reduction, better adherence to mineral aggregates or fibres or to reduce the inflammability [1 - 3].

Plain polymer concrete is used due to its good chemical resistance, impermeability and high strength for drainage systems, high quality boards or sanitary appliances. Using the fast hardening and strength development of special resins polymer concrete is a rapid repair material for cement concrete e.g. on highways, runways or bridges [4 - 7]. The adhesion of thermosetting resins to cement concrete is generally greater than the tensile strength of the concrete.

Polymer concrete has - like cement concrete - a relatively low tensile strength compared with its compressive strength. With structural applications tensile reinforcement may therefore be required.

POLYMER CONCRETE

The binder for the polymer concrete of this investigation was an orthophthalic polyester resin with shrinkage reducing additives. In additional tests a hybrid resin consisting of polyester and polyurethane compounds was used. The resin content for all mixes was 12 %. The aggregate was crushed quartz with maximum grain size of 5 mm and chalk powder. The compressive strength at 23 °C was with 128 MPa very high, the flexural strength of 25 MPa corresponded - like with cement concrete - to one fifth of the compressive strength. The polymer concrete produced with the hybrid resin had a compressive strength of 136 MPa when cured at 23 °C and of 140 MPa when cured at 60 °C. The flexural strength was 27.5 MPa and independent on the curing temperature. As the mechanical properties of polymers depend on temperature, the materials properties were determined at 23, 40 and 60 °C (see Table 1).

Table 1: Properties of polyester concrete at 23, 40 and 60 °C

Temperature °C	Compressive strength MPa	Flexural strength MPa	Modulus of elasticity MPa
23	128	25.1	28200
40	120	24.4	25200
60	118	19.3	24400

Polymers and therefore also polymer concretes are viscoelastic materials with long-term behaviour depending on stress depending on stress and temperature [8, 9]. Bending creep tests were performed at 23, 40 and 60 °C with a stress equal to 50 % of the corresponding short-term strength. The creep deformation measured as deflection was at 60 °C 273 % bigger than at 23 °C for a loading time of 1000 hours (see Table 2). Tests after ending of the creep tests at the respective temperature did not show any loss in flexural strength due to the long-term loading.

Table 2: Creep deformation after 1000 hours loading with 50 % of the short-term strength

Temperature °C	Flexural stress MPa	Creep deformation µm	Deformation increase %
23	12.6	33	0
40	12.2	73	121
60	9.7	123	273

Tests over 1000 hours (about 1.4 month) do not of course cover the lifetime of polymer concrete, which may be 25 years or more. To overcome the need for tests over the expected lifetime, relations were developed to extrapolate the creep deformation over one or two decades of time, so that only tests lasting a reasonably short time have to be conducted. For this the relation $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 + m \cdot t^n$ derived by Findley [10] is often used, where ε is the total deformation, ε_0 the elastic deformation and m and n are constants, with m depending on the stress and n being independent of it. When the creep deformation is plotted versus the time in a double logarithmic scale a straight line appears. The graphical extrapolation over one or two decades of time can easily be performed.

Applying this graphical method - as shown in Figure 1 - the creep deformations would have doubled between 1000 and 100000 hours (11.4 years) loading time. The extrapolated creep deformations for 25 years are given in Table 3. The creep coefficients, which give the relation of creep deformation to elastic deformation, are also listed.

Table 3: Creep deformation extrapolated for 25 years and creep coefficients

Temperature	23 °C	40 °C	60 °C
Creep deformation	72 µm	169 µm	282 µm
Creep coefficient	0.47	1.36	1.09

Figure 1: Bending creep at 50 % of the flexural strength, extrapolation to 25 years

REINFORCEMENT

The steel reinforcement used for the tests consisted of ribbed steel rebars with different diameters. The yield strength - taken from literature - was 550 MPa, the modulus of elasticity 200 000 MPa. The non-metallic reinforcement bars were made from E glass fibres bonded with polyester resin. The rebars had a square cross-section of 8 mm or a diameter of 22 mm. The surface was textured for better adherence to the surrounding concrete. The glass fibre content was about 60 % by weight. The ultimate strength of the GFRP (glass fibre reinforced plastic) rebars was about 1000 MPa, the modulus of elasticity about 45000 MPa. The stress-strain relationship was linear up to failure. The GFRP had a strength about 60 % higher than the steel but only about 20 % of the steel-stiffness (see Figure 2).

STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

1. Preliminary tests without steel reinforcement

Polyester concrete beams only with tension reinforcement or with tension and compression reinforcement - but without stirrups as GFRP stirrups were not available - of GFRP rebars of 8 mm

square cross-section exhibited an unsatisfactory load bearing behaviour. From the type of failure could be concluded that shear reinforcement e.g. stirrups would increase the load bearing capacity and that the GFRP rebars due to their composition with single fibres and the relative low modulus of elasticity do not yield an effective compression reinforcement. Therefore for further tests GFRP rebars were only used as tension reinforcement.

2. Polyester concrete beams

The cross-section of the 1500 mm long beams was 200 mm (height) and 100 mm (width). The upper reinforcement consisted of two steel rebars with 6 mm diameter. As lower (tension) reinforcement four 8 mm square GFRP rebars or three steel rebars with 16 mm diameter were arranged. The distance of the steel or GFRP rebars from the top or bottom face of the beams was 20 mm. The beams were so designed that the maximum tensile force the reinforcement was able to carry was the same for the GFRP (at tensile strength) and for the steel (at yielding). Stirrups of 5 mm diameter of mild steel were arranged at a distance of 100 mm. The tests were conducted as 4-point bending tests with a distance of the supports (steel rollers of 50 mm diameter) of 1200 mm. The load was applied over steel rollers (diameter 50 mm) at a distance of 400 mm from the supports. Figure 3 shows the test setup. The deflection was recorded in all tests. The stress in one of the GFRP rebars of the beams with combined reinforcement was measured with strain gauges at the centre of the span, 300 and 550 mm from the centre.

Figure 2: Stress strain relation for steel and GFRP rebars

Figure 3: Test setup for bending tests of beams

The failure occurred with the GFRP reinforced beams after opening of wide cracks, splitting of the concrete along the GFRP rebars and crushing of the concrete in the areas, where load was applied (see Figure 4). The stress in the GFRP rebars increased slowly until cracks opened in the area where the strain gauges were located. Depending on the location of cracks in relation to the strain gauges the tensile stresses in the GFRP rebars nearly reached the tensile strength (see Figure 5).

Figure 4: Beam with GFRP tension reinforcement after failure

Figure 5: Stress in GFRP rebar in relation to applied bending moment

The beams with steel tension reinforcement failed on yielding of the steel when crushing of the concrete close to the load inducing rollers occurred (see Figure 6). In Table 4 details of the tension reinforcement and test results are given.

Table 4: Reinforced polyester concrete beams

Tension reinforcement	GFRP	Steel
Rebars	4 □ 8 mm	3 Ø 14 mm
Area	256 mm ²	462 mm ²
Weight per meter	0.41 kg/m	3.84 kg/m
Tensile force at strength / yielding ¹⁾	256 kN	254 kN
Failure moment	38.7 kNm	45.8 kNm

Figure 6: Beam with steel tension reinforcement after failure

- 1) GFRP: tensile strength 1000 MPa
Steel: yield stress 550 MPa

The deflection of the beams in relation to the applied bending moment was for both reinforcements nearly equal before the first cracks opened. Afterwards the deflection of the beams with GFRP rebars increased about 6 times faster than for the steel reinforced beams. The deflection of the beams with GFRP rebars increased nearly linearly in the progress of the loading due to the pure elastic properties of the GFRP rebars. The beams with steel rebars showed a distinct increase in the deflection at the yield point of the steel (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Deflection of beams with steel or GFRP tension reinforcement

Figure 8: Level crossing

3. Level crossing slabs

Level crossing slabs are arranged between the rails or as connection to the adjacent road and are subjected to the static and dynamic loads from the road traffic (see Figure 8). The level crossings slabs tested had an overall length of 1448 mm, were 600 mm wide and 120 mm thick. The slabs were either reinforced with steel rebars welded into a cage or an upper reinforcing steel grid, which corresponded to the upper layer of the reinforcing cage, and a lower layer of GFRP rebars of 22 mm diameter. The load was applied via a 42 mm thick wooden panel (cross laminated) on an area of 200 mm x 500 mm in approximation to the wheel of a truck. The distance of the supports - steel rollers with 50 mm diameter - was 1330 mm (see Figure 9). In Table 5 details of the tension reinforcement and test results are given.

The load-deflection behaviour for the level crossing slabs was very similar to the beams. Up to the cracking load of the slabs nearly the same deflections were measured independent on the type of reinforcement. At higher loads, the deflection of the GFRP reinforced slabs was about twice as large as the deflection of the slabs with steel tension reinforcement (see Figure 10).

Table 5: Reinforced polyester concrete beams

Tension reinforcement	GFRP	Steel
Rebars	6 Ø 22 mm	8 Ø 16 mm
Area	2280 mm ²	1610 mm ²
Weight per meter	4.5 kg/m	12.5 kg/m
Tensile force at Strength / yielding ²⁾	2280 kN	886 kN
Ultimate load	235 kNm	310 kNm

- 2) GFRP: tensile strength 1000 MPa
Steel: yield stress 550 MPa

Figure 9: Level crossing slab at bending test

The slabs with GFRP rebars in the tension zone failed suddenly when the polyester concrete burst off the rebars (see Figure 11). The slabs with steel reinforcement failed on yielding of the steel and crushing of the concrete as the compression zone decreased due to the increasing deflection (see Figure 12). Figure 13 shows a slab with GFRP tension reinforcement after unloading at the end of the test, when the GFRP rebars due to their fully elastic properties had become straight again while the steel rebars remained deformed.

Figure 10: Deflection of level crossing slabs with steel or GFRP tension reinforcement

Figure 11: Level crossing slab with GFRP rebars after failure

Figure 12: Level crossing slab with steel reinforcing cage after failure

Figure 13: Level crossing slab with GFRP rebars after unloading at the end of the test

CONCLUSIONS

The investigations conducted with polymer concrete (binder: orthophthalic polyester resin) at temperatures of 23, 40 and 60 °C showed that higher temperatures resulted only in a small decrease in compressive strength, a relatively large decrease in flexural strength and a very large increase in creep deformation.

Bending tests on polyester concrete beams or level crossing slabs with steel or GFRP tension reinforcement resulted in larger deflections of the GFRP reinforced specimens. This can be attributed to the stiffness of the GFRP which was only about 20 % the stiffness of the steel.

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